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A Surgical Technique for the Treatment of Bladder Exstrophy

INTRODUCTION

Despite more than a century of investigation, the problem of surgical correction of bladder exstrophy remains highly relevant. Bladder exstrophy is a severe congenital malformation with an incidence of 1:15,000–40,000 live births.

To date, there is ongoing debate regarding the optimal timing of surgical correction and the choice of operative technique. This is due to the high rate of unsatisfactory functional outcomes, primarily concerning urinary continence, as well as the development of severe complications involving the urinary tract, including ascending infections resulting from the mixing of urine and feces.

The variety of surgical procedures proposed reflects the absence of a universal method capable of providing stable and satisfactory functional outcomes.

Currently, two principal surgical approaches are recognized:

1. Reconstruction of the bladder using local tissues.
2. Creation of an artificial bladder.

The use of native tissues for bladder reconstruction is considered the most pathogenetically justified approach. However, this technique is feasible only when the bladder plate is of sufficient size and favorable anatomical conditions are present. The recommended timing for primary reconstruction is within the first 72 hours of life, with mandatory restoration of the pubic symphysis and creation of an internal urethral sphincter mechanism. Given the duration and complexity of the procedure, the infant must have adequate body weight and no severe associated congenital anomalies.

Since these conditions are not met in all newborns, formation of an artificial bladder represents an alternative strategy. A significant drawback of such procedures is the high risk of urinary tract infections, potentially leading to secondary renal scarring and chronic kidney disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Between 2000 and 2012, 22 children with bladder exstrophy were treated at our institution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In five patients, surgical reconstruction using local tissues was performed during the neonatal period (between 2 and 10 days of life). The outcomes were considered unsatisfactory.

In two patients, postoperative wound dehiscence and failure of the bladder plate sutures were observed (in one case, pubic symphysis repair was not performed; in the other, surgery was carried out on the 10th day of life).

In one patient, prior to epispadias correction, agitation led to evagination of the bladder through a 0.3 cm anterior abdominal wall defect, necessitating emergency cystectomy.

In two patients, the reconstructed bladder demonstrated poor functional performance, with persistent urinary incontinence and recurrent exacerbations of chronic urinary tract infection. These children remain under long-term follow-up, receive rehabilitative therapy, and are being evaluated for further surgical management.

Fifteen patients underwent formation of an artificial bladder with urethral reconstruction between 2 and 8 years of age.

Five patients were operated on after the age of 10 years, including three who had previously undergone unsuccessful reconstruction with local tissues.

In twelve patients, an artificial bladder was primarily constructed using the technique developed at our institution. Long-term outcomes were considered satisfactory.

In three patients previously operated on using the earlier version of the technique, retraction of the inter-reservoir septum necessitated neo-urethral reconstruction using a modified approach.

Two patients who had undergone surgery at other institutions according to the A.V. Melnikov technique required repeat reconstructive surgery using the proposed method due to severe urinary incontinence, fecal calculi formation, and significant urinary tract infection (at ages 12 and 14 years, respectively).

A surgical method for the treatment of bladder exstrophy was developed (Patent No. 30906, dated March 11, 2008).

The procedure includes a lower midline laparotomy with excision of the bladder plate and transection of the ureters at their orifices, followed by mobilization of the sigmoid colon to an adequate length for perineal descent.

The rectum is transected at its junction with the sigmoid colon, and the proximal end is closed. The ureters are implanted into the rectal lumen using an invagination technique, followed by two-layer closure of the rectal stump.

At the level of the peritoneal reflection, the seromuscular layer of the rectum is incised along the anterior semicircumference, and mucosal stripping is performed distally along nearly the entire semicircumference, leaving a 1 cm mucosal strip at the 5–6 o'clock position.

From the perineal side, the mucosa is excised in a conical fashion, and a neo-urethral channel not exceeding 1 cm in diameter is created using a continuous suture.

The sigmoid colon is descended intrarectally, and mucocutaneous sutures are placed circumferentially at the level of the anus and the newly formed urethra.

From the abdominal side, the edges of the rectal muscular layer are fixed to the descended colon, and the pelvic floor is peritonized.

During the procedure, the reservoir is irrigated with a 1–2% povidone-iodine solution.

This technique ensures that the newly formed urethra and the descended colon are positioned within the rectal sphincter complex, thereby facilitating continence and preventing the mixing of urine and feces.

Outcomes were evaluated 12 months postoperatively. Long-term follow-up (up to 7 years) was available for 12 patients.

Assessment included patient complaints, clinical evaluation of urinary and fecal continence, presence or absence of urine-feces mixing, status of the ureters and kidneys (based on ultrasound and excretory urography), and laboratory blood and urine parameters. In recent years, endoscopic evaluation of the constructed reservoir has also been performed.

Results were rated as good in eight patients and satisfactory in four.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Surgical treatment of bladder exstrophy is reconstructive in nature.
2. Correction of the defect is staged and requires an individualized approach.
3. The surgical technique for artificial bladder formation developed at our institution provides satisfactory functional outcomes and may be considered the method of choice when primary reconstruction using local tissues is not feasible.

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